

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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COMPARING READMISSION RATES BETWEEN PHYSICIAN AND
PHYSICIAN/ACNP TEAM

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

Heart failure (HF) is the most common and costly reason for readmission. The acute care nurse practitioner (ACNP) is the ideal advanced practice nurse (APN) to help manage HF patients in the hospital setting. The aim of this study was to determine readmission rate differences when an ACNP was involved in the management of HF patients. This retrospective study was conducted to compare all-cause, unplanned 30-day readmission rates in HF patients managed by a physician alone versus a physician/ACNP team, in a single community hospital setting. Patient demographic variables were analyzed to determine their association with readmission rates. Slightly longer lengths of stay were found in the physician/ACNP group but ranges between groups varied ($p = .03$). The odds of being readmitted increased by a factor of 2.2 for each hospitalized day during the initial admission (OR, 2.156; 95% CI; $p < .0001$). Results demonstrated greater odds for readmission in the physician group but was not statistically significant (OR, 2.632; 95% CI; $p = .07$). Inversely, the odds of being readmitted decreased with ACNP involvement (OR, 0.38; 95% CI; $p = .07$) but again was not statistically significant. Being admitted in the 12 months prior to this study was associated with readmission during the study period ($p = 0.07$). Utilization of ACNPs in the hospital setting may help reduce readmission rates in HF patients and may offer relief in other chronic disease related readmissions.

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BACKGROUND

Cost of Healthcare

Since 2010, the hospitalization cost per inpatient day averages between \$1,629 to \$1,910 in the United States, and \$2,566 in California (Henry J. Kaiser Family Foundation, 2010). According to the study conducted by Heidenreich et al. (2013), the estimated costs in treating heart failure (HF) in the United States in 2012 was \$20.9 billion in 2012 and is expected to rise to \$53.1 billion in 2030. Eighty percent of these costs are attributed to hospitalizations. High readmission rates (RRs) have been identified as a costly and preventable (Hedenreich et al., 2013). Between 17% and 19.6% of adult patients are readmitted within 30 days of discharge and 34% are readmitted within 90 days (Jencks, Williams, & Coleman, 2009; Stranges, Barret, Wier, & Andrews, 2012). According to the statistical brief issued by the Agency for Health Care Policy and Research (Elixhauser, Au, & Steiner, 2013), HF is the number one reason for rehospitalization with 24.7% of patients readmitted within 30 days.

Readmitted patients have longer lengths of stay; approximately 13 to 30 days per patient, compared to patients not readmitted whose length of stay averages 5 to 12 days (Cooper, Sirio, Rotondi, Shepardson, & Rosenthal 1999; Kramer, Higgins, & Zimmerman, 2013). In addition to longer lengths of stay, patients readmitted to hospital have significantly higher mortality rates post readmission discharge, and have a higher incidence of being readmitted into an intensive care unit (ICU; Cooper et al., 1999; Kramer et al., 2013). According to Harjola et al. (2010), 42% of patients readmitted with HF were readmitted into an ICU. Patients readmitted to an ICU have a 24% mortality rate when compared to a rate of 4% in patients not readmitted into an ICU (Cooper et al.,

1999). These findings are consistent with the Kramer et al. (2013) study, which demonstrated a 21% mortality rate in patients readmitted to an ICU when compared to a rate of 4% in patients not admitted to an ICU.

Healthcare Reform

Medicare 2004 data indicate \$17.4 billion in healthcare costs were related to unplanned readmissions (Jencks et al., 2009). As a result, the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) contracted with Yale New Haven Health Services Corporation/Center for Outcomes Research and Evaluation (YNHHSC/CORE) to analyze readmission rates among Medicare beneficiaries (YNHHSC/CORE, 2012). This research group developed a complex formula to estimate the 30-day all-cause readmission rates (RRs) for HF, myocardial infarction, and pneumonia, and reported the result as a risk-standardized readmission rate (RSRR). The group collected data from hospitals across the United States between 2008 and 2010. The highest reported RSRR was found in HF with an RSRR score of 25%. The CMS now publicly reports the RSRR on the Hospital Compare website at <http://hospitalcompare.hhs.gov> which is updated annually (YNHHSC/CORE, 2012).

On March 23, 2010, due to increasing medical costs and poor quality outcomes, President Barak Obama signed the Affordable Care Act (ACA) into law. The purpose of the ACA is to improve access to care, improve quality of care, and reduce healthcare costs (Kocher, Emanuel, & DeParle, 2010). Pay-for-performance initiatives and bundled payments are some of the ACA measures currently implemented. Hospital Value-Based Purchasing (HVBP) is a pay-for-performance approach established by the ACA and initiated by the CMS (2012a).

Since 1982, hospitals have received reimbursements based on the Diagnosis-Related-Group (DRG; CMS, 2001). DRGs are groupings of diagnoses in which Medicare pays one flat rate per DRG (CMS, 2001). In 2013, DRG payments were reduced by 1% and will be further reduced to 1.25% by the end of 2014 (CMS, 2012a, 2012b). The end savings are being utilized to fund the HVBP incentive payments to eligible hospitals. HVBP are initiative payments made to hospitals for high Total Performance Scale (TPS) scores. TPS is weighted on the following domains: Clinical process of care at 70%, and patient experience of care at 30%. Clinical process of care includes complying with national standards and core measures in areas such as heart failure. For example, prescribing a beta-blocker and angiotensin-converting-enzyme inhibitor to HF patients on discharge is a HF core measure. Patient experience includes communication with patients and families, such as providing dietary and fluid restriction education to HF patients prior to discharge. This score is then compared to a national benchmark. Higher TPS scores result in higher incentive payments, while lower scores result in no additional payments to the institution or providers (CMS, 2012a, 2012b).

Another ACA initiative is the Hospital Readmissions Reduction Program which became effective October 1, 2012 (CMS, 2013b). The Hospital Readmission Reduction Program allows CMS to penalize hospitals for patient readmissions within 30 days of discharge in the areas of HF, AMI, and pneumonia (CMS, 2013b). As of 2013, the penalty for excess readmissions in any of these areas can reach as high as a 1% reduction per DRG reimbursement. This penalty is expected to increase to 2% by the end of 2014 (CMS, 2013b). As a result, many hospitals are implementing the evidence-based HF guidelines endorsed by organizations such as the American Heart Association and

College of Cardiology to reduce HF readmissions (Heidenreich et al., 2013). Despite these efforts, HF remains among the top reasons for all-cause hospital readmissions, with an estimated 46% of all hospital admissions being related to HF (Jencks et al., 2009).

As part of healthcare reform, CMS is also phasing out the current fee-for-service payments and replacing the fee-for service reimbursement with one bundled payment in which the hospital receives one fixed payment per episode of illness (CMS, 2013a; Schroeder & Frist, 2013). The payment covers the patient 3 days prior to admission through 30 days, translating into no additional monies if the patient is readmitted within this time frame (CMS, 2013a; Schroeder & Frist, 2013).

Provider Shortage

The Affordable Care Act has begun implementing measures to improve access to medical care by insuring 34 million uninsured Americans (Manchikanti, Caraway, Parr, Fellows, & Hirsch, 2011). This influx of newly insured Americans will increase the number of people seeking medical care. In addition, there is an increasing aging population requiring advanced health care (Heidenreich et al., 2013). There are currently more than forty million Americans over the age of 65 with a projected eighty million seniors by 2040 (Young, Chaudhry, Rhyne, & Dugan, 2010). According to Heidenreich et al. (2013), the number of Americans over the age of 80 living with HF is expected to increase 66% by the year 2030. Thus, there will be more individuals living with HF who will require advanced medical care (Heidenreich et al., 2013).

Unfortunately, the number of physician providers available to care for this growing population has continued to decline (Young et al., 2010).

Role of the Nurse Practitioner in the Acute Care Setting

The decrease in physician availability was recognized in 2003 after the implementation of the resident duty-hour restrictions imposed by the Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education (ACGME), which limited the number of hours residents are able to work (Patores et al., 2011). In 2010, the ACGME applied further resident hour restrictions in some of the more critical patient care areas requiring hospitals to find ways to fill the gaps in patient care. As a result, the number of nurse practitioners (NPs) in the hospital setting increased (Patores et al., 2011).

NPs are advanced practice nurses (APNs) with advanced clinical training beyond their professional registered nursing preparation. NPs complete a graduate degree program specializing in a particular area of practice and are prepared to practice in primary care, acute care, and/or long-term care facilities (American Association of Nurse Practitioners [AANP], 2011). NPs work autonomously or in collaboration with health care professionals depending on each state's regulating body. NPs provide a full range of services including ordering and interpreting tests, diagnosing and treating acute and chronic conditions, prescribing medications and treatments, educating and counseling, conducting research, and translating research into clinical practice. There are approximately 167,000 NPs currently practicing in the United States (AANP, 2011).

Acute care nurse practitioners (ACNPs) make up the fifth largest specialty area of NP practice (American Nurses Credentialing Center [ANCC], 2009). ACNPs receive training in diagnostic imaging interpretation, electrocardiogram interpretation, ventilator management, advanced life support, and various invasive procedures (ANCC, 2009; Melander et al., 2008). The ACNP training is focused on caring for patients in the acute

care setting, which separates the ACNP from other NP subspecialties (Melander et al., 2008). The majority of ACNPs are practicing in suburban and inner city hospital settings (ANCC, 2009; Kleinpell & Goolsby, 2012). Several studies have reported positive feedback from hospital personnel regarding ACNPs in the hospital setting related to their accessibility in the inpatient setting, their role in care coordination, and the high quality patient care they provide (Hoffman, Happ, Scharfenberg, DiVirgillio-Thomas, & Tasota, 2004).

Heidenreich et al. (2013) emphasizes the need for a multidisciplinary approach in caring for HF patients. HF patients have multiple comorbidities, are older, and many are living with advanced disease. With the growing number of patients living with HF and increasing complexities in treating these patients, there will be a greater need for specialized APNs to help manage these patients (Heidenreich et al., 2013).

Problem Statement

The strain of increasing healthcare costs, changes in reimbursement, demands for high quality and complex care, an increasing aging population, and provider shortages are resulting in hospital closures (Hsia, Kellermann, & Shen, 2011). Nationwide, 42 acute care hospitals filed bankruptcy between 2000 and 2006, and emergency departments in non-rural areas declined by 27% between 1990 and 2009 (Hsia et al., 2011; Landry & Landry, 2009). Those most affected were community hospitals (Hsia et al., 2011). Community hospitals, as defined by the American Hospital Association, are non-federally funded, short-term, general hospitals with services available to the public (Hsia et al., 2011). Underserved populations rely heavily on community hospitals for their care and

without them, patients may be forced to travel long distances for care, delaying treatment and oversaturating neighboring hospitals (Hsia et al., 2011).

According to the study conducted by Hsia et al. (2011), community hospitals most at risk for closures were those serving low income communities of color. These community hospitals demonstrated an 11% increase in RR among low income patients of Black or Hispanic descent (Hsia et al., 2011). Heart failure is the most common reason for readmission, and is most prevalent in blacks (Joynt et al., 2011). Readmissions increase utilization of resources and prolong hospitalizations (Elixhauser et al., 2013; Hsia et al., 2011; Landry & Landry, 2009; Stranges, et al., 2012). High RRs have arguably been associated with poor quality of care, resulting in reductions in reimbursement and added penalties via the Hospital Value-Based Purchasing and Hospital Readmission Reduction Programs (Jencks et al., 2009; YNHHS/CORE, 2012).

Readmissions are costly and many are preventable. As a result, many policy makers and hospitals are focusing on strategies to reduce RRs (Jencks et al., 2009; YNHHS/CORE, 2012). Heidenreich et al. (2013) estimate HF in Black men to increase an additional 29% by the year 2030. In addition, the number of Americans living with HF is expected to increase to more than 8 million by 2030, with 26% over the age of 80 (Heidenreich et al., 2013). Annual costs in treating people between 65 and 79 year of age are projected to increase from current expenditures of \$11.5 billion to over \$29.93 billion (Heidenreich et al., 2013). However, there are an inadequate number of physician providers to care for these patients (Young et al., 2010). By 2035, the United States is estimated to see a shortage of 130,000 practicing physicians (Young et al., 2010).

Purpose

The purpose of this study was to compare all-cause, unplanned 30-day RR on HF patients managed by a physician alone versus HF patients managed by a physician and ACNP team, in one community hospital setting.

Research Questions

The project sought to answer the following questions:

1. Was there an association between demographic variables and 30-day readmission in this sample?
2. How did patients discharged with a diagnosis of HF and readmitted within 30 days differ in demographics between the physician alone and the physician/ACNP team?
3. Was there a difference in 30-day RR and length of stay in patients initially discharged with a diagnosis of HF when managed by a physician alone versus managed by a physician/ACNP team?
4. What demographic characteristics of HF patients most likely predicted their readmission within 30 days of discharge?

Supporting Framework

The theoretical framework being utilized as the underpinnings for his project is the Chronic Care Model (CCM) developed by Edward H. Wagner in 1998 (Epping-Jordan, Pruitt, Bengoa, & Wagner, 2004; Wagner et al., 2005). The CCM is a patient-centered approach which promotes patient involvement in care while supporting provider use of evidence-based practices. This model was utilized by the ACNP under investigation, as the framework for her practice. The model looks at two major settings

and four interacting components to produce desired patient outcomes (Epping-Jordan et al., 2004; Wagner et al., 2005).

The two major settings include the community and the health system (Epping-Jordan et al., 2004; Wagner et al., 2005). In the community setting, the CCM promotes the utilization of community resources. In the health system, the CCM advocates surveillance of performance to promote better practices by assessing the institution's goals and leadership qualities to determine congruency with patient-centered care (Epping-Jordan et al., 2004; Wagner et al., 2005). The ACNP in this study works only in the inpatient setting and participates in the surveillance of performance, which is utilized by the institution to promote better practices.

The four interacting components of the CCM include self-management support, delivery system design, decision support, and clinical information systems (Epping-Jordan et al., 2004; Wagner et al., 2005). The self-management component supports patient participation in healthcare planning and maintenance (Epping-Jordan et al., 2004; Wagner et al., 2005). The ACNP in this study educates the patient about their disease and need for compliance prior to discharge. This education includes discussions with heart failure patients regarding diet, exercise, daily weights, fluid intake, medication compliance, and follow up. The delivery system design supports the idea that health systems are organized in a way that supports patient-centered care (Epping-Jordan et al., 2004; Wagner et al., 2005). The ACNP in this study utilizes the institution's resources and staff to ensure coordination of care from admission to discharge. This includes providing information to discharge planners, social workers, health care agencies, and outpatient primary care providers to aid in the transition from hospital to home. The

decision support component involves the utilization of evidence-based practices and strategies to promote best practices (Epping-Jordan et al., 2004; Wagner et al., 2005).

The ACNP in this study utilizes the hospital's database system to ensure she is practicing within current guidelines. She works closely with patients and families to incorporate patient needs with evidence-based treatment. The clinical information system component requires that the medical team utilize technology to collect patient information, compare patient outcomes with national benchmarks, plan care, provide patient information, and track patients (Epping-Jordan et al., 2004; Wagner et al., 2005). The ACNP in this study utilizes the hospital's electronic medical record to document the patient's progress and initiate a plan of care. In addition, the ACNP utilizes the electronic medical record to track her team's compliance with core measures. All of these functions were part of the role of the ACNP in managing acutely ill patients in this hospital setting.

A study conducted by Retrum et al. (2013) found five common themes in patients readmitted with HF, which included worsening symptomatology on readmission, difficulty in self-management at home, psychological factors, and fractionated care within the delivery system. Policy makers and organizations such as the American Heart Association and the American Academy of Cardiology have all emphasized adherence to HF guidelines. However, even with implementation of these guidelines, there is little change in readmission rates among HF patients, and the numbers are estimated to rise in the coming years (Heidenreich et al., 2013). Ketterer, Draus, McCord, Mossallam, and Hudson (2013) found depression, substance abuse history, and other psychosocial history and behaviors were also good predictors for readmission in HF patients. These types of studies demonstrate the multifaceted reasons for readmissions among HF patients. To

make a significant impact on readmission rates among HF patients, these patients require a holistic approach in managing their care (Ketterer et al., 2013; Retrum et al., 2013).

NPs promote self-care and behavior modifications, apply evidence-based practices, utilize telemedicine, and are comfortable with a multidisciplinary approach to coordinating patient care, which makes the CCM an ideal model for nurse practitioners (McCauley, Bixby, & Naylor, 2006; Ortiz & Fromer, 2011; Watts et al., 2009). Since this model is utilized by the ACNP under study investigation, the model is being utilized as the underpinnings for this study to explore if adding an ACNP to a physician team will improve coordination of care and thereby reduce RRs in HF patients.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A literature search was conducted utilizing PubMed, CINAHL, and Cochrane databases. The search terms used were “nurse practitioner AND readmission(s) AND heart failure.” MeSH terms included “nurse,” “advanced practice nurse,” “advanced practice registered nurse,” “nurse provider,” “acute care nurse practitioner,” “allied health,” “mid-level provider,” “hospital,” “rehospitalization”, and “admission(s).” Due to the lack of recent relevant articles, older publications dating as far back as 1998 were included in the review. After exhausting all searches, the review considered ten articles that discussed hospital readmission outcomes in relation to NPs and HF, and two other articles which focused on hospital readmission outcomes in relation to NPs and patients with other chronic diseases. Five of these 12 articles utilized the NP in a case management role with no treatment management practices; therefore, these five articles were discarded. In addition, there were few research articles found that studied the effect of ACNPs on RRs; however one was related to ACNPs and neurosurgical outcomes which was included in this review. The literature critique can be found in the table of evidence (Appendix A).

Dahl and Penque (2001) conducted a retrospective, pre-post design study that involved 1,192 inpatients diagnosed with heart failure in one large metropolitan hospital. The study compared patient outcomes before and after implementation of an advanced practice nurse (APN) heart failure program. The APN program consisted of both a NP and clinical nurse specialist. The APN training and clinical background were not discussed in this study. The APNs in this study assessed and educated patients on HF,

conducted discharge planning, and made HF management suggestions to the primary team. The results demonstrated a reduction in length of stay by 14% in the APN intervention group (t -test, $p < .05$), as well as a 90-day reduction in RRs (Chi-square, $p = .046$). The authors attributed these results to the APN providing a more comprehensive management approach (Dahl & Penque, 2001).

Dahle, Smith, Ingersoll, and Wilson (1998) conducted a retrospective, pre-post design study which compared patient outcomes before and after implementation of a NP led HF program at one large teaching institution. The sample consisted of 215 patients admitted with uncomplicated HF. The study did not discuss the NP's background or training. The NP in this study admitted and treated all uncomplicated HF patients. Treatment was based on a HF protocol created by the NP in collaboration with an attending physician. The NP made daily rounds, amended the plan of care, and performed discharge planning. After implementation of the NP led HF program, there was a total hospital savings of \$133,000 over 1 year and a savings of \$1,400 per patient, which was statistically significant when costs were compared to pre-intervention ($p < .03$). The author attributed these savings to a decrease in unnecessary testing and therapies. Unlike the Dahl and Penque study, reductions in length of stay and RRs were not found to be statistically significant (Dahle et al., 1998).

Lowery et al. (2012) undertook a quasi-experimental design study which included 969 male patients with HF from four veteran hospitals and one outpatient veterans' clinic. The study explored HF patient outcomes when managed by a physician versus being managed by an NP. Both physician and NP groups implemented national HF guidelines and were allowed to modify the guidelines to fit their patients' needs. The NPs were

trained and experienced in cardiac care. The NPs in this study assessed and monitored patient symptoms, implemented clinical pathways, managed medications, educated patients, and coordinated care with other specialists. Like the Dahl and Penque (2002) study, results demonstrated a decrease in RRs (Logistical Regression, $p < .001$) and reduction in length of stay (Logistical Regression, $p = .015$) in the NP group when compared to the physician group. The authors suggest having NP disease management programs in place is an inexpensive and effective strategy to caring for patients unable to receive physician care (Lowery et al., 2012).

Naylor et al. (2004) conducted a randomized-control study which involved 239 patients, over the age of 65, with heart failure. The study took place at six academic and community hospitals. The study explored patient outcomes both before and after implementation of a heart failure program led by APNs. The APNs specialized in geriatrics and utilized an evidence-based protocol as a guideline to manage inpatients and outpatients with HF. The APNs were able to tailor the protocol to individualize treatment. After implementation of the APN program, results demonstrated lower RRs at 52 weeks (Cox Regression, $p = .01$) and per patient year (Cox Regression, $p < .001$), and also demonstrated longer times to readmission (Kaplan-Meier Log Rank, $p = .026$). These findings are similar to the studies conducted by Dahl and Penque (2001) and Lowery et al. (2012), which also demonstrated lower RRs and lengths of stay after implementation of an APN. Naylor et al. also demonstrated a decrease in hospital costs after implementation of the APN program ($p = .002$), with a mean savings of \$4,845 per patient. This cost savings is much higher than what was noted in the Dahle et al. (1998) study. However the Dahle et al. study was conducted 3 years prior and in taking account

for inflation rate changes, the large savings in the Naylor et al. study was comparable. The patients in the study also reported an improved quality of life at 12 weeks (Wilcoxon Rank Sum test, $p < .05$), and greater satisfaction with care (Naylor et al., 2004; Wilcoxon Rank Sum test, $p < .001$). The study did not look at length of stay. Although the authors did mention the APNs were specialized in geriatrics, they did not specify the type of APNs utilized (i.e., clinical nurse specialist versus NP). It is reasonable to assume the APNs in this study were NPs because the APNs were able to manage the patients' medications and other therapeutics; however, there could have been a mixture of APNs as in the Dahl and Penque study.

Russell, VorderBruegge, and Burns (2002), undertook a retrospective, quality improvement project which involved 524 neurosurgical patients in an intensive care unit (ICU) setting at one large teaching hospital. The study explored neurosurgical patient outcomes treated by an ACNP versus treated by internists and residents. The ACNP in this study performed daily rounds, completed progress notes and history and physicals, reviewed diagnostics, and ordered tests and therapeutics. In addition, the ACNP utilized literature searches to ensure best practices. Results demonstrated a decrease in length of ICU stay (One-way analysis of variance, $p < .001$), and in overall hospital stay (One-way analysis of variance, $p = .03$) in the ACNP intervention group when compared to the internist/resident group. There was also a decrease number of urinary tract infections and skin breakdown in the ACNP group (Chi-square analysis, $p < .05$). The total 1-year savings in the ACNP group amounted to \$2,467,328. However, there were no statistically significant differences noted in RRs between the ACNP group and the internist/resident group. The researchers noted the decrease in length of stay and

reduction in infections contributed to the savings to the hospital. They suggested the decrease in length of stay and infections were most likely related to having the ACNP established in the unit, allowing for immediate availability and close monitoring of patients (Russell et al., 2002). Although this was not a HF-ACNP intervention, this study helps to understand the role of the ACNP in the acute care setting.

Key Factors Associated With Readmissions

Several key factors associated with readmissions are discussed in this section.

Increasing age is a well-studied factor associated with a high prevalence for HF and high RRs in patients already diagnosed with HF (Muzzarelli et al., 2010; Schocken et al., 2008; Shamma, Khan, Nekkanti, & Movahed, 2007). With regard to gender differences, studies have demonstrated slightly higher RRs among women with ischemic heart disease when compared to men, but the higher numbers have not been shown to be significantly different (Babayan et al., 2003; Lee, Capra, Jensvold, Gurwitz, & Go, 2004; Schocken et al., 2008; Shamma et al., 2007). In addition, the incidence of low left ventricular systolic function is higher in men than women, while the incidence for preserved left ventricular systolic function is higher in women than in men (Shamma et al., 2007). However, studies have not shown significant differences in RRs or in hospital length of stay between patients with preserved ventricular systolic function versus patients with low left ventricular systolic function (Malki et al., 2002; Retrum et al., 2013).

A factor affecting readmission rates is race. Blacks with HF have higher morbidity rates and a 13% higher 30-day readmission rate (RR) than white persons with HF (Joynt et al., 2011; Schocken et al., 2008). According to Joynt et al. (2011), this 13% RR for Blacks jumps to 25% when treated at a minority-serving hospital. Income and

insurance are other factors associated with readmission rates. Low-income earning HF patients have higher 30-day RRs when compared to HF patients with higher earnings (Lindenauer et al., 2013; Schocken et al., 2008). Several studies have demonstrated higher RRs, longer lengths of stay, and poor outcomes among patients with HF having either Medicare, Medi-Cal, or no insurance (Allen et al., 2012; Elixhauser et al., 2013; Kapoor et al., 2011; Malki et al., 2002).

Zaya, Phan, and Schwarz (2012) found higher propensity for readmissions in HF patients who fell into one of one of three categories: disease-centered, physician-centered, or patient-centered. In the disease-centered category, progression of heart disease, co-morbidities, and infections all contributed to more frequent hospital readmissions. In the physician-centered category, late or missed detection and treatment of disease, poor discharge planning, poor coordination of care, and no communication were all associated with more frequent readmissions. In the patient-centered category, poor compliance with treatment, no follow-up with primary care provider, and poor understanding of disease all contributed to more frequent readmissions (Zaya et al., 2012).

Co-morbidities have also been shown to be a factor on readmission rates in patients with HF but vary depending on the type, number, and severity of the co-morbidity (Muzzarelli et al., 2010; Schocken et al., 2008; Shamma et al., 2007; Thakar Parikh, & Liu, 2012). For example, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, valvular heart disease, ischemic heart disease, and obesity have all been identified by the American Heart Association as major clinical risk factors for HF, but RRs vary between the disease types (Schocken et al., 2008). Acute kidney injury in conjunction with HF on initial

admission has a high rate for readmission within 30 days of discharge but is often related to worsening renal failure (Shammas et al., 2007; Thakar et al., 2012). Other comorbidities including anemia and depression have also been associated with high RRs, but reasons for readmissions vary (Muzzarelli et al., 2010; Shammas et al., 2007). Annema, Luttk, and Jaarsma (2009) looked at reasons for readmissions in HF patients and demonstrated 64% were readmitted for cardiovascular reasons, of which 32% were directly related to worsening HF. The remaining 36% were readmitted for non-cardiovascular related issues (Annema et al., 2009). Several studies have demonstrated increased lengths of stay and hospital costs in patients readmitted to hospital (Cooper et al. 1999; Elixhauser et al., 2013; Hsia et al., 2011; Kramer et al., 2013; Landry & Landry, 2009; Stranges et al., 2012).

Another factor contributing to RRs in HF patients is physician workload. The study conducted by Joynt, Orav, and Jha (2013) compared heart failure 30-day readmission rates between physicians caring for a high volume of HF patients and physicians caring for a low volume of HF patients, and found 30-day RRs were highest among the high volume physicians ($p < .001$). Low volume was operationalized as caring for less than eight HF patients per year, and high volume was operationalized as caring for eight to fourteen HF patients per year (Joynt et al., 2013).

METHODS

Design

This was a retrospective study of patients with HF who were readmitted within 30 days of a prior hospitalization. Existing data were analyzed to determine differences in HF RRs between a physician alone and a physician and ACNP team. One board-certified physician and one board-certified ACNP were chosen for this project as a convenience sample to evaluate RRs among a physician alone versus the same physician with an ACNP working together as a team. Between the periods of March 2011 through November 2011, the physician worked alone at the study hospital; March 2012 through November 2012, an ACNP was employed to work alongside of the physician as an MD/ACNP team. Information including patient demographics, provider workload differences, and diagnoses at discharge and readmission were obtained during the two identified time periods, first when the physician worked as a solo provider and then when the ACNP became a team member.

Sample

The patient sample was identified by reviewing an existing hospital log of all HF patients in one community center hospital. There were a total of 190 patients with HF whose information was recorded in the HF log. Patients discharged by any other physician or expiring prior to initial discharge were excluded as subjects. The total number of eligible participants was 190 based on the inclusion criteria. The 190 subjects were then divided into two categories: Group 1 included all patients discharged by the physician alone with a discharge date between March 2011 through November 2011 ($n =$

81). Group 2 included all patients discharged by the physician/ACNP team with a discharge dated between March 2012 through November 2012 ($n = 109$).

Setting

The study was conducted at a community hospital within southern California. The hospital is a for-profit, acute care hospital with over 350 beds and is located in an inner-city area with a population of over 100,000. The hospital serves a low-income community which is predominately Black and Hispanic. Services include emergency medicine, critical care, obstetrics, rehabilitation, cardiac care, radiology, and surgical care.

Data Collection

Data were obtained utilizing the hospital's "heart failure patient log" for the medical providers and dates of hospitalization including the two time periods of interest in this study. The patients were divided into two groups, as noted in the sample section. The demographic and patient characteristic variables that were measured in this study had been identified in prior research studies as key factors associated with readmissions. Therefore, these variables were included for analysis in this research study.

The HF log contained a list of all patients admitted, readmitted, and discharged with HF. This record contained demographic information of interest to this study (i.e., age, race, and insurance coverage), as well as the initial admitting and readmitted diagnosis, number of prior admissions, length of stay, and provider type. Demographic variables were analyzed to determine if there were significant differences between the two groups of patients (i.e., physician or physician/ACNP managed groups) at the time of initial hospital admission and at the time of readmission, if this occurred. This analysis

was conducted to determine whether demographic variables were covariates that would affect the outcome measure (RRs). The number of readmissions within 30 days was also noted on the log. Age was coded in years, and race was coded as White, Black, Asian, Hispanic, or other on the HF log. Insurance was identified by the name of the insurance company and was obtained from the log. Type of insurance was used as a proxy for income. Propensity for readmissions is defined as having at least one admission within the prior 12 month period before the initial admission under investigation in the identified timeframe of the study. For example, if a Group 2 subject had been admitted in January 2012 and again in April 2012, the subject would be labeled as one having a propensity for readmission due to an admission (January 2012) within the prior 12 month period from the start of Group 2 data collection. The number of readmissions was obtained from the HF log and was utilized to determine differences in readmissions between the physician alone and physician/ACNP team.

Level of income was not part of the HF log and was therefore not investigated in this study. However, Medi-Cal (Medicaid) is a government funded insurance program which insures low income people and was used as a proxy measure of low income status (Howell, 1998; Kapoor, et al., 2011). Insurance company information was obtained from the log and coded by the name of the insurance company listed on the log.

Severity of heart failure disease is primarily measured utilizing the New York Heart Association (NYHA) functional classifications and classified utilizing the criteria as shown in Figure 1.

Class	Functional Capacity
I	Patients with cardiac disease but resulting in no limitation of physical activity. Ordinary physical activity does not cause undue fatigue, palpitation, dyspnea or anginal pain.
II	Patients with cardiac disease resulting in slight limitation of physical activity. They are comfortable at rest. Ordinary physical activity results in fatigue, palpitation, dyspnea or anginal pain.
III	Patients with cardiac disease resulting in marked limitation of physical activity. They are comfortable at rest. Less than ordinary activity causes fatigue, palpitation, dyspnea or anginal pain.
IV	Patients with cardiac disease resulting in inability to carry on any physical activity without discomfort. Symptoms of heart failure or the anginal syndrome may be present even at rest. If any physical activity is undertaken, discomfort increases.

Figure 1. New York Heart Association functional classification criteria. Adapted from “Classes of Heart Failure” by the American Heart Association, 2011.

Severity of disease was not part of the hospital’s HF log; however most heart failure patients admitted to hospital fall within a NYHA classification of either III or IV (Ahmed, Aronow, & Fleg, 2006). A study conducted by Holland, Rechel, Stepien, Harvey, and Brooksby (2010) demonstrated RRs are similar between NYHA classifications III and IV. Inclusion of the NYHA classification was not included in the hospital’s HF log. Furthermore, the researcher believes it would not provide significant information as to the RRs in this study. Co-morbidities have also been shown to increase RRs. However RRs vary depending on the type, number, and severity of co-morbidities; therefore they were not considered in this study.

To identify the provider workload’s association with RRs, the average number of patients seen by the physician, before and after the implementation of the ACNP, was obtained. This number was compared to other solo hospitalist physicians and other

hospitalist physician/allied health professional (NP or Physician Assistant) teams. This patient to provider ratio was collected from hospital's department of medical staffing. Length of stay on initial admission and readmission was also obtained from the HF log and coded by days in hospital. Ejection fraction measurements were not collected, as the literature review demonstrates no difference in hospital length of stay or RRs in patients with preserved ventricular systolic function versus patients with low left ventricular systolic function.

Reliability checks were performed by a random selection of 5 charts from both sample groups for a total number of 10 charts reviewed. The information in these 10 hospital records was compared to the information provided on the HF log. There was 100% accuracy between what was reported in the log and what appeared in the medical records as validated in a blind review of the medical records by the researcher.

Data Analysis

An independent biostatistician with no association to this study was employed to assist with this study's data analysis. The primary outcome measure was to determine readmission differences between the physician alone and the physician/ACNP team. Univariate analysis on patient characteristics between various group comparisons as listed in Tables 1 and 2 was done using *t*-tests or Wilcoxon rank sum tests, where appropriate for continuous variables, and chi square test of independence or Fisher exact test for categorical variables. A *p*-value of 0.05 was considered to be significant. All analyses were performed using SAS version 9.3. Descriptive statistics for continuous variables were presented as mean and standard deviation scores, or as median and range score. For categorical variables, results were expressed as frequency and valid percent. Multivariate

logistical regression was used to identify factors that predicted the dependent outcome variable (i.e., 30-day readmission rate). The independent variables tested were age, length of stay, group (physician alone and physician/ACNP team). The inclusion of other covariates led to an unstable model fit due to few readmission events. Overall model performance was measured using Hosmer and Lemeshow tests and Nagelkerke's *R*-squared statistics, a measure of explained variance.

Ethical Considerations

Plans to ensure the protection of human subjects were presented to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) and committee for approval. The main strategy was deidentification of the patient record. Permission was obtained from the hospital to conduct the study. The research involved a review of records and therefore did not meet criteria for a full Institutional Review Board (IRB) review. A waiver was granted by IRB at California State University Los Angeles (see Appendix B). To ensure patient protection and provider anonymity, all identifiable information was removed and transposed onto an excel spreadsheet where the medical record numbers were recoded to random numbers. A separate excel spreadsheet was utilized to link the medical record numbers to the recoded numbers. This spreadsheet was kept in a locked closet, in an undisclosed location, only known by the researcher. This spreadsheet was utilized to identify the medical records to be reviewed for the reliability check as discussed in the Data Collection section. Only those medical records utilized for the reliability testing were accessed. In addition, hospital staff members were blinded to the study's purpose.

RESULTS

Demographic and Readmission Differences

The final sample consisted of 190 patients selected for this study with 81 in the physician alone group and 109 in the physician/ACNP group. Age, financial class, and race were analyzed to determine whether there were significant differences in these variables between the two groups during their initial admission in the timeframe studied. There were no significant differences noted between the groups ($p > 0.05$) for the variables age, financial class (using type of insurance as proxy), and race. Of the 190 patients in this study, 24 were readmitted within 30 days of initial discharge. Patients readmitted did not differ in age, financial class, or race based on the whether the patient was admitted or not admitted. Readmitted patients had a mean age of 65.3 (SD 14.4) years compared to the mean age of 60.5 (SD 14.4) in those not readmitted; most of patients had Medi-Cal or Medicare insurance (Table 1). Black race made up the majority of this sample. One finding of interest was the number of readmissions in patients with a recent history of admission (18/24). Seventy-five percent of patients readmitted within 30 days of initial discharge had a prior admission within 12 months of the study periods; confirming a propensity for readmission. Patients not readmitted within 30 days of initial discharge had no prior admissions within 12 months of the study periods (0/166). In addition, patients in the readmitted group had a longer initial length of stay, with a median stay of 4 days (2-12 days), when compared to patients not readmitted, who had a median stay of 3 days (1-9 days), $p < .001$ (Table 1).

Table 1

Demographic Variables and 30-Day Readmissions

Demographic variable (<i>n</i> = 190)	Readmitted in 30-Days		<i>p</i> -Value
	No (<i>n</i> = 166)	Yes (<i>n</i> = 24)	
Age - mean (<i>SD</i>)	60.5 (13.8)	65.3 (14.4)	0.11 ^a
Financial class			0.15 ^b
Fee for service	3 (100.0)	0 (0)	
Medi-Cal	62 (86.1)	10 (13.4)	
Medicare	76 (84.4)	14 (15.6)	
No insurance	25 (100.0)	0 (0)	
Race			0.54 ^b
Black	136 (88.3)	18 (11.7)	
White	28 (82.4)	6 (17.7)	
Other race	0.02 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	< 0.0001 ^c
Initial length of stay	3.0 (1-9)	4 (2-12)	
Previous admissions in prior 12 months	0.0 (0)	18 (75.0)	n/a

Note: Values are means (*SD*), median (range), and *n* (%).

Tests used to determine significance:

^a *T*-test

^b Fisher Exact test

^c Wilcoxon rank sum test

n/a = not applicable, all events happen in one group

Demographic and Readmission Differences Between Groups

Fisher Exact test and *t*-tests were performed utilizing the entire sample size (*N* = 190) to investigate the effect of demographic variables on 30-day readmission. The majority of the study's population was of Black race with all other race categories having either none or small numbers. As a result, the sample was dichotomized to Blacks and other (Table 2). Race, age, and financial class did not demonstrate statistically significant differences between group readmission rates (Table 2).

Patients in the physician/ACNP group had a slightly longer, statistically significant length of stay, with a median of 5 days (4-11 days), when compared to the

patients in the physician alone group, which had a median length of stay of 4 days (2-12 days; $p = .03$). The range of stay in the physician/ANCP group spanned 7 days while the physician range spanned 10 days. The physician alone patient group had a length of stay whose range was 1 day longer and 2 days shorter than its counterpart team group (Table 2).

Table 2

Demographic Variables Between Groups

Demographic variable	Group		<i>p</i> -Value
	MD alone (<i>n</i> = 11)	MD/ACNP team (<i>n</i> = 13)	
Age - mean (<i>SD</i>)	63.6 (15.5)	67.4 (13.4)	0.54 ^a
Financial class (<i>n</i> , %)			0.24 ^b
Medi-Cal	7 (53.8)	3 (27.3)	
Medicare	6 (46.2)	8 (72.7)	
Race (<i>n</i> , %)			0.17 ^b
Black	8 (61.5)	10 (90.9)	
Other race	5 (38.5)	1 (9.1)	
Length of Stay, initial admit median (range)	4 (2-12)	5 (4-11)	0.03 ^c

Note: Values are means (*SD*), median (range), and *n* (%). MD = physician, MD/ACNP = physician and acute care nurse practitioner.

Tests used to determine significance:

^a *T*-test

^b Fisher Exact test

^c Wilcoxon rank sum test

Multivariate logistic regression was used to identify factors which predicted the outcome variable, 30-day readmissions (Table 3). Independent variables that reached a *p*-value < 0.10 were maintained in the final model. The independent variables tested were length of stay and management group. Inclusion of other covariates led to an unstable model fit due to fewer outcome events. Overall model performance was measured using

Hosmer and Lemeshow test and by Nagelkerke's R-squared statistics, a measure of explained variance. Table 3 illustrates the results of these analyses. The odds of readmission is 2.63 times greater in MD alone group compared to MD/ACNP group; however, this is not statistically significant ($p = 0.07$). Inversely, the odds of being readmitted is 0.38 times less when an ACNP is involved, and again the results were not significant ($p = 0.07$). However, a trend was noted in the data toward the MD and ACNP team as a potential variable influencing readmission rates. For a 1 day increase in initial LOS, the odds of being readmitted (versus not being re admitted) increases by a factor of 2.2 ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3

Logistical Regression Analysis for Predictors of 30-Day Readmissions (n = 190)

Variable	Beta	SE	OR	95% CI	p-Value
Length of stay	0.768	0.162	2.156	(1.568-2.964)	< 0.0010
Group (Ref MD/ACNP)	0.968	0.531	2.632	(0.930-7.452)	0.0683
Intercept	-5.266	0.827			
Group (Ref MD alone)	0.968	0.531	0.380	(0.134-1.075)	0.0683
Intercept	-4.298	0.685			

Another factor the research attempted to adjust for was workload. Research demonstrates higher workload is associated with higher readmission rates (Joynt et al., 2013). The physician and physician/ACNP team in this study managed fewer patients than other hospitalists and hospitalist/allied health provider teams within this hospital (Table 4). However, the physician practiced in other institutions and as a result, the researcher was unable to reveal the physician's actual workload. Therefore, no further analysis was conducted on this factor.

Table 4

Workload Data

MD hospitalists	Average # of pts seen 3/2011 - 11/2011
MD under investigation	898
MD hospitalist #2	2,246
MD hospitalist #3	1,120
MD hospitalist #4	1,346
MD/mid-level hospitalist team	Average # of pts seen 3/2012-11/2012
MD/ACNP team under investigation	1,246
Team #2	3,104
Team #3	2,133

Additional statistical analysis was conducted to evaluate for differences in readmission diagnosis and length of stay between groups and no differences were noted ($p < 0.05$ for all).

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to determine differences in readmission rates between HF patients managed by a physician alone versus HF patients managed by a physician/ACNP team. First, the researcher sought to determine an association between demographics and 30-day readmissions. No differences in age, financial class, or race between patients admitted and patients not readmitted were demonstrated. The median age of the sample was 65 years, which is consistent with the findings from Heidenreich et al.'s (2013) study who reported a high incidence of patients, 65 years and older, living with HF. The readmitted patients in the study were insured with either Medi-Cal or Medicare; therefore the hospital subject to CMS penalties that may have affected decisions about length of stay. The data were consistent with several studies noting higher readmission rates in HF patients insured under Medicaid or Medicare (Allen et al., 2012; Elixhauser et al., 2013; Kapoor et al., 2011; Malki et al., 2002).

The race of the majority of the sample was Black (80%). Seventy-five percent of those readmitted were also of Black race. These findings are similar to those found in the Joynt et al. (2011) study which also reported a high prevalence for HF among Blacks. The readmitted patients in this study experienced slightly longer lengths of stay which is similar to other studies reporting longer lengths of stay for readmitted patients (Cooper et al., 1999; Kramer et al., 2013). There was a wider range in the readmitted group from 2 to 12 days when compared to the not admitted group, which was from 1 to 9 days. Patients in this research study had shorter readmission lengths of stay than other studies reporting readmission lengths of stay between 13 to 30 days (Cooper et al., 1999; Harjola et al., 2010; Kramer et al., 2013). The hospital in which this study was conducted serves

a large HF patient population predominately of Black race. As a result, this hospital's provider(s) and ancillary staff may have more experience in treating patients with HF and may have provided better management than institutions in other studies.

The investigation also sought to evaluate the demographic differences between patients readmitted in the physician alone group and patients readmitted in the physician/ACNP group. No demographic differences were seen between the physician and physician/ACNP team. There was a slight increase in the initial length of stay in the physician/ACNP team (5 days) when compared to the physician alone (4 days). These findings were inconsistent with several studies which found a shorter length of stay with NP involvement (Dahl & Penque, 2001; Dahle et al., 1998; Lowery et al., 2012; Russell et al., 2002). It is important to note the wide range in the initial length of stay in the physician alone group (2 to 12 days) as compared to the physician/ACNP group (4 to 11 days). Considering the small sample size in this study, this broad range may be the result of outliers and/or may reflect a worsening severity of illness in the physician/ACNP group.

In evaluating the differences in readmission rates between the physician alone and the physician/ACNP team, the readmitted group ($n = 24$) was too small to adequately detect differences in readmission rates based on provider care. As a result, the hypothesis for differences in probability for readmission between the physician and physician/ACNP team was not supported by study's findings. However, the data were trending towards significance ($p < .10$) with ACNP involvement and may be worth reexamining this hypothesis in future studies with a larger sample size. Other studies with larger sample

sizes have demonstrated lower readmission rates with NP involvement (Dahl & Penque, 2001; Lowery et al., 2012; Naylor et al., 2004).

An additional component that emerged from this study was the propensity for readmission. Being admitted within 12 months prior to the study was strongly associated with readmission during the time periods under investigation. Propensity for readmissions falls into one of three categories: disease-centered, physician-centered, or patient-centered (Zaya et al., 2012). Based on data obtained from the HF log, the researcher could not determine the category(s) these readmitted patients belonged. Nonetheless, this study demonstrates a recent admission increased propensity for readmissions.

Much of the research reviewed in preparation for this study did not elaborate on the educational and professional background of the APN. APNs are specialized and focus on specific areas of practice (ANCC, 2009). The ACNP in this study was a newly graduated ACNP. She received training in the hospital setting during her graduate program and had 6 years of hospital nursing experience prior to ACNP practice. Her ACNP training included the utilization of the Chronic Care Model which is the framework she utilizes in practice. In collaboration with her physician, she managed patients from admission to discharge, and ensured compliance to core measures per hospital policies. She also facilitated discharges through patient education, timely referrals, and coordinated care with other healthcare providers.

The most significant limitation to this study was the sample size ($n = 190$). The findings from this study demonstrated a lower readmission rate (13%) than the national average (17%-20%). The small sample size ($n = 190$) could explain this low readmission

rate. The studies reported in the literature review had much larger sample sizes when compared to this study.

This retrospective study relied on pre-existing data from a HF log. Information pertaining to HF management was not included in this record. In addition, other confounding variables such as co-morbidities, compliance, and severity of illness were not included in the record. Controlling for these variables in future studies may prove beneficial in better determining an association between provider effects on readmission rates. Lastly, this researcher was not able to fully appreciate the influence of workload on readmission rates. Providers often practice in different sites and settings, as was the case in this study. Further research is needed with a larger sample to evaluate these relationships.

Summary

The strain of increasing healthcare costs, changes in reimbursement, demands for high quality, complex care, increasing aging population, and provider shortages are resulting in hospital closures (Hsia et al., 2011). These stressors have been identified in hospital readmissions which is most prevalent among Black persons with HF (Hsia et al., 2011).

Utilization of the ACNP in the hospital setting may help reduce readmission rates in heart failure patients as well as for those with other chronic disease. This study is one of the few studies evaluating the effect of ACNPs on readmission rates. In addition, this is the only study of its kind discussing a ACNPs chosen framework in practice, the Chronic Care Model of Management, and its effect on readmissions. As the nation's

hospital population increases and provider access decreases, more studies are needed to evaluate the effectiveness of ACNPs in the acute care setting.

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APPENDIX A
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Summary of Studies

Article	Purpose & Design	Sample/Setting and Intervention	Measurement Tools	Results	Authors' Conclusions	Limitations/Threats to Validity
Dahl, J., Penque, S. (2001). The effects of an advanced practice nurse-directed heart failure program. <i>Dimensions of Critical Care Nursing</i> , 20(5), 20-28.	<p>Purpose: To determine if an inpatient HF program managed by an APN affects PT outcomes.</p> <p>Design: Retrospective, pre-post design. Compared pre-program to post-program outcomes.</p>	<p>Sample: 1,192 PTs with principal diagnosis of HF at admission or D/C.</p> <p>Setting: 572 bed hospital in a large metropolitan area in the Midwest.</p> <p>Intervention: Guided by evidence & an NP, 2 graduate APN students, 1 NP & 1 CNS, assessed, educated & performed D/C planning on HF PTs, and made suggestions for care.</p>	DRGs to identify HF PTs and class. <i>T</i> -tests to evaluate LOS differences. Chi-square analysis to analyze RRs.	Those in APN directed group had: 14% reduction in LOS ($p < 0.05$), 90-dy RR decreased ($p = 0.046$)	The APNs facilitated a more comprehensive management approach.	Limitations of a retrospective design, nonrandomized. Could not positively attribute positive patient outcomes to the effects of the APN program. Did not track RR from three other local area hospitals.
Dahle, K., Smith, J., Ingersoll, G., & Wilson, J. (1998). Impact of a NP on the cost of managing inpatients with HF. <i>American Journal of Cardiology</i> , 82(5), 686-688.	<p>Purpose: To investigate the impact of the NP on outcomes.</p> <p>Design: Retrospective, pre-post test. Compared data from before and after implementation of the NP.</p>	<p>Sample: 215 PTs who attended a HF program at Vanderbilt Medical Center.</p> <p>Setting: Teaching hospital</p> <p>Intervention: NP admitted all uncomplicated HF. HF protocol created by NP & MD was utilized. NP developed care plan in</p>	Vanderbilt hospital administrative database to review outcomes. DRG 127 to identify candidates for the program.	After implementation of the NP: Total hospital costs were lower ($p < 0.03$), with a cost saving per PT of \$1,400 & total year savings of \$133,000, LOS was shorter ($p = 0.13$) but not statistically significant. Also RR	Hospital savings was due to decrease use in unnecessary testing and therapeutics. These finding suggest that management of	PTs were not randomized. Decrease in number of testing done may be due to the fact the NP PTs were not as sick. Authors did not state type of NP utilized

Article	Purpose & Design	Sample/Setting and Intervention	Measurement Tools	Results	Authors' Conclusions	Limitations/ Threats to Validity
		collaboration with the attending MD, made daily rounds, amended plan of care, & performed D/C planning.		was also not significantly different.	uncomplicated HF PTs by NPs result in cost savings.	specialty, background, or education.
Lowery, J., Hopp, F., Subramanian, U., Wiitala, W., Welsch, D., Larkin, A., . . . Vaitkevicius, P. (2012). Evaluation of a nurse practitioner disease management model for chronic heart failure: A multi-site implementation study. <i>Congestive Heart Failure</i> , 18(1), 64-71.	<p>Purpose: To evaluate the effectiveness of a NP led HF program.</p> <p>Design: Quasi-experimental. Both MD group & NP group received national guidelines. Compared outcomes on the two groups.</p>	<p>Sample: $n = 969$, majority men, mean age 66. Included all PTs with systolic or diastolic dysfunction. Excluded PTs with < 6 month to live.</p> <p>Setting: 4 midwest VA inpatient settings & 1 outpatient setting</p> <p>Intervention: NP monitored PT symptoms, implemented clinical pathways, medication management, educated PTs, & coordinated care with other specialists.</p>	<p>VA national PT database to determine RR, LOS, outpatient visits.</p> <p>VA beneficiary identification records for mortality rates</p> <p>VA pharmacy benefits database for medication prescribing and use.</p>	<p>All cause RR were lower in the NP group ($p < 0.001$).</p> <p>Higher number of outpatient clinic visits in the NP group ($p < 0.001$)</p> <p>Decrease in LOS in the intervention group ($p = 0.015$).</p>	NP disease management programs may be less expensive than MD directed care and feasible for medical centers and clinics in areas without access to cardiologists.	Lacked randomization. Primarily a male population and only included VA facilities, limits generalizability.
Naylor, M., Brooten, D., Campbell, R., Maislin, G., MCAuley, K., & Schwartz, J. (2004). Transitional care of older adults hospitalized with heart failure: a	<p>Purpose: To examine the effectiveness of a transitional care intervention delivered by APNs to elders hospitalized with HF.</p> <p>Design: RCT. Compared outcomes</p>	<p>Sample: $n = 239$ PTs > 65, admitted to hospital with diagnosis of HF, oriented, & resided < 60 miles from hospital. Excluded end stage renal disease PTs.</p> <p>Setting: 6 academic & community hospitals</p>	<p>Telephone interviews to determine RR.</p> <p>Minnesota Living with HF Questionnaire to determine quality of life.</p>	<p>Intervention group: Lower readmissions at 52 weeks ($p = .01$), longer times to readmission ($p = .026$), less readmissions per patient year ($p < .001$), lower total costs ($p = .002$) & mean savings</p>	This flexible protocol guided APNs, enabling them to individualize treatment. Readmissions were	Did not elaborate on type of APN, specialty, experience, education or training background. Patient satisfaction tool

Article	Purpose & Design	Sample/Setting and Intervention	Measurement Tools	Results	Authors' Conclusions	Limitations/ Threats to Validity
randomized, controlled trial. <i>Journal of American Geriatric Society</i> , 52(2), 675-684.	before implementation of the APN program and after implementation of the program.	Intervention: APNs were masters prepared & specialized in geriatrics. They utilized an evidence-based protocol as baseline, then individualized it. APNs made daily visits on admission then intermittent home visits for 3 months.	Investigator developed tool to assess PT satisfaction. Medicare reimbursements used to estimate resource costs.	of \$4,845/ PT & reported: Greater overall quality of life at 12 wks ($p < .05$), & greater satisfaction with care ($p < .001$). Control group: High number of PTs with > 3 readmissions ($p < .001$).	decreased in the intervention group and PTs overall had better outcomes.	not validated.
Russell, D., VorderBruegge, M., & Burns, S. (2002). Effect of an outcomes-measured approach to care of neuroscience patients by acute care nurse practitioners. <i>American Journal of Critical Care</i> , 11(4), 353-362.	Purpose: To determine the clinical and financial impact of an outcomes-managed model on 2 NS, ACNP managed vs non-ACNP managed units. Design: Retrospective, quality improvement project. Compared two units. One managed by an ACNP & one by intern/residents only.	Sample: $n = 524$ PTs NS ICU. Setting: NS ICU & ward at a university teaching hospital. Intervention: ACNP performed daily rounds, reviewed diagnostics, completed H&P, monitored clinical status, ordered tests, therapeutics with MD collaboration, & rounded	ICD-9 to determine diagnostic codes for sampling purposes. Monitoring tool created by the ACNP from a literature search to ensure best practices.	ACNP managed group: Mean LOS in ICU decreased ($p < .001$), overall LOS decreased, ($p = .03$), & decreased number of UTIs & skin breakdown ($p < .05$). Total 1 year savings over 1 year was \$2,467,328, which included LOS savings. No significant difference in RR.	ACNP performed early interventions contributing to reduce LOS. D/C planning was initiated by the ACNP early in the hospital course.	Was not a RCT. Care elements could not be directly linked to the effect of the ACNP intervention. Use of ANCP was not compared to other APN models. Was not a HF intervention.

Note. APN(s) = Advanced Practice Nurse(s); Pt(s) = patient(s); HF = heart failure; D/C = discharge; NP = nurse practitioner; CNS = clinical nurse specialist; DRGs = Diagnosis-Related-Groupings; LOS = length of stay; RR(s) = readmission rates(s); MD = physician; NS = neurosurgical.

APPENDIX B

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD WAIVER

Office Memorandum

DATE: March 14, 2014

TO: Thomas W. Barkley, Jr./Anna Carchi
Nursing, NSS

FROM: E. Amaro, Institutional Review Board – Human Subjects

COPIES TO: S. Ulanoff, Chair; J. Shitsugu, Executive Secretary

SUBJECT: Review of Project Involving Human Subjects

Applicant: Thomas W. Barkley, Jr./Anna Carchi

Title: Comparing 30-Day Readmission Rates between Physician and
Physician/Nurse Practitioner Team

Application #: IRB W13-4

Date of Review: November 18, 2013

Action: Approved 1/17/14
 Convened committee
 Expedited (reviewed and approved by IRB chair or designee)
 Denied - see below
 Tabled - see below
 Administrative Action Waiver
 Informed Consent:

Office of Research and Development